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**Modulating Excitation/Inhibition Balance through tES: Physiological
Mechanisms in Animal Models.**

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Running title: tES and E/I Balance in Animal Models

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41 Abstract

42 The balance between excitatory and inhibitory (E/I) activity is a fundamental property
43 of neural circuits, ensuring precise information processing and preventing pathological
44 states such as hyperexcitability or network silencing. Disruptions in this balance have
45 been linked to several neurological and psychiatric disorders, including epilepsy, autism,
46 and schizophrenia. Transcranial electrical stimulation (tES) can modulate the E/I balance
47 through mechanisms that affect synaptic plasticity, neurotransmitter systems, and
48 network synchronization. The main tES modalities—transcranial direct current
49 stimulation (tDCS), transcranial alternating current stimulation (tACS), and transcranial
50 random noise stimulation (tRNS)—operate through distinct physiological principles,
51 enabling the modulation of neuronal excitability and oscillatory dynamics. Animal
52 models offer controlled experimental conditions to study the effects of tES on E/I
53 regulation at the cellular, synaptic, and network levels. Preclinical research has revealed
54 polarity-dependent plasticity with tDCS, frequency-specific entrainment with tACS, and
55 GABAergic modulation with tRNS. These findings are essential for validating
56 computational models and refining stimulation protocols. Future studies should
57 integrate multimodal technologies to enhance the translational relevance of tES and
58 develop personalized neuromodulation strategies targeting E/I imbalance in brain
59 disorders.

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68 Introduction

69 The balance between excitatory and inhibitory (E/I) activity in the brain is essential for
70 normal brain function and neural activity (Tatti et al., 2017). Cortical neurons integrate
71 glutamatergic and GABAergic inputs to maintain optimal membrane potentials and
72 enable adaptive responses (Landau et al., 2016). Disruptions in this balance contribute
73 to disorders such as epilepsy, autism, and schizophrenia (Eichler & Meier, 2008; Yizhar
74 et al., 2011; Nguyen et al., 2016). The E/I balance is shaped by synaptic plasticity
75 mechanisms proposed by Hebb (1949) and later extended to include inhibitory circuits
76 (Saraga et al., 2008; D'amour & Froemke, 2015). Non-invasive stimulation techniques
77 like tDCS, tACS, and tRNS may help restore E/I balance depending on brain region and
78 context (Krause et al., 2013; Van Bueren et al., 2023).

79 Transcranial electrical stimulation (tES) is a non-invasive technique that applies weak
80 electrical currents to the scalp, modulating cortical excitability and inducing immediate
81 and lasting effects on brain function (Nitsche & Paulus, 2000; Woods et al., 2016). The
82 main tES modalities include transcranial direct current stimulation (tDCS), which uses
83 low-intensity direct currents to modulate excitability depending on polarity, and
84 transcranial alternating current stimulation (tACS), which applies oscillatory currents to
85 influence brain rhythms (Paulus, 2011). tDCS has been widely studied in motor learning,
86 cognition, depression, and stroke (Nitsche & Paulus, 2000; Nitsche et al., 2008; Brunoni
87 et al., 2012), while tACS shows promise in conditions such as schizophrenia, epilepsy,
88 and Alzheimer's disease (Herrmann et al., 2013; Antal & Paulus, 2013; Kasten et al.,
89 2016). A third variant, transcranial random noise stimulation (tRNS), delivers broadband
90 random currents that enhance neuroplasticity and show promise in perception,
91 memory, and clinical applications (Fertonani et al., 2011; Snowball et al., 2013; Van Der
92 Groen & Wenderoth, 2016). The therapeutic potential of tES may lie in its ability to
93 modulate fundamental neural processes, such as the balance between excitatory and
94 inhibitory (E/I) activity in the brain (Krause et al., 2013).

95 Given the limitations of studying E/I balance directly in humans, animal models are
96 essential for uncovering the physiological and molecular effects of tES. They offer
97 controlled conditions to examine both immediate and long-term effects (Sánchez-León

98 et al., 2018) and allow systematic variation of parameters such as intensity, frequency,
99 and duration. Furthermore, they permit invasive assessments of neuronal activity,
100 neurotransmission, and plasticity-related pathways (Jackson et al., 2016).

101 This mini-review highlights the contribution of animal models to uncovering how tES
102 modulates the E/I balance, offering controlled settings to dissect the underlying
103 physiological mechanisms.

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106 Transcranial Electrical Stimulation in Animal Models

107 Animal models enable researchers to adapt tES protocols to non-human species,
108 optimizing experimental conditions by adjusting electrode placement, current intensity,
109 and stimulation duration to account for anatomical and physiological differences
110 between animals and humans. To achieve targeted stimulation, researchers use smaller
111 electrode sizes and precise skull placement, while higher current densities help
112 compensate for differences in brain volume and conductivity (Márquez-Ruiz et al., 2014;
113 Jackson et al., 2016).

114 Animal models offer versatility for studying tES across multiple levels with both *in vitro*
115 and *in vivo* approaches. *In vitro* models, especially brain slices, yield insights into cellular
116 and synaptic mechanisms, including membrane polarization, synaptic plasticity, and
117 neurotransmitter dynamics (Bikson et al., 2004, 2012; Radman et al., 2009; Kabakov et
118 al., 2012). *In vivo* models enable exploration of network and behavioral effects.
119 Experiments in anesthetized animals permit detailed circuit-level analysis and
120 connectivity changes (Ozen et al., 2010; Opitz et al., 2016; Vöröslakos et al., 2018), while
121 awake animals provide key insights into neuromodulatory effects on behavior and
122 cognition (Márquez-Ruiz et al., 2012; Monai et al., 2016; Krause et al., 2017; Sánchez-
123 León et al., 2018, 2021).

124 By integrating cutting-edge techniques such as high-density electrophysiology (Krause
125 et al., 2022; Farahani et al., 2024; Sánchez-León et al., 2025), two-photon imaging
126 (Monai et al., 2016; Gellner et al., 2021), optogenetics (Fröhlich & McCormick, 2010;

127 Mabil et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2021), and chemogenetics (Su et al., 2024), animal
128 models provide unparalleled opportunities to investigate the effects of tES. These
129 modern approaches, when combined with classical electrophysiological techniques—
130 including intracellular and extracellular recordings—offer unprecedented resolution for
131 dissecting stimulation-induced changes. This multimodal strategy enables the
132 investigation of tES-induced alterations at both the cellular and network levels,
133 advancing our understanding of its mechanisms and potential therapeutic applications
134 (Table 1).

135 Animal models bridge basic and clinical research, enabling disease-specific insights
136 (Sánchez-Garrido Campos et al., 2025). In Alzheimer’s models, gamma-frequency
137 optogenetic stimulation of parvalbumin interneurons improved memory and synaptic
138 plasticity, likely by reducing amyloid-beta (Iaccarino et al., 2016; Etter et al., 2019).
139 Similarly, gamma-tACS applied for 20 min restored impaired LTP in mice (Jeong et al.,
140 2021). Although the current density used in this animal study was not reported, human
141 studies applying gamma-tACS for longer durations (60 min) have shown significant
142 improvements in memory performance in patients with mild cognitive impairment due
143 to Alzheimer’s disease (Benussi et al., 2021), supporting the direction of the findings
144 observed in animal models. In epilepsy, cathodal tDCS (3.54 mA/cm², 25 min) reduced
145 seizures and restored E/I balance in anesthetised rodents (Sun et al., 2020). In clinical
146 settings, cathodal tDCS applied for a similar duration (30 min) but with markedly lower
147 current density (0.057 mA/cm²) has been shown to reduce seizure duration in patients
148 with mesial temporal lobe epilepsy and hippocampal sclerosis (Tekturk et al., 2016). In
149 Parkinson’s models, anodal tDCS (0.88 mA/cm², 20 min) enhanced motor function
150 through dopaminergic activation (Tamura et al., 2024). Comparable stimulation in
151 patients—anodal tDCS over the motor cortex for 20 min—has led to significant
152 improvements in gait speed, step length, and cadence, although at a substantially lower
153 current density (0.057 mA/cm²) (Schabrun et al., 2016). While tRNS has shown promise
154 in humans (Van Der Groen et al., 2022), its mechanisms remain unclear due to scarce
155 preclinical data (Antal & Herrmann, 2016).

156 Building on the methodological framework established in animal models, we next
157 investigate how tES modulates the E/I balance through synaptic-level mechanisms.

158 Table 1. Summary of the impact of transcranial electrical stimulation techniques (tDCS, tACS,
 159 tRNS) on synaptic plasticity, molecular and cellular mechanisms, and neural network dynamics
 160 based on animal model studies. Key references from animal research supporting each described
 161 mechanism are provided. An asterisk indicates that the mechanism has also been observed in
 162 humans.

	Synaptic Plasticity	Molecular and Cellular Mechanisms	Neural Networks Dynamics
tDCS	Polarity-dependent effects: anodal stimulation facilitates LTP-like plasticity, while cathodal induces LTD-like plasticity in animal models* [Bindman et al., 1964; Bikson et al., 2004; Kronberg et al., 2017; Sánchez-León et al., 2025].	Modulates calcium channels* , requires NMDA receptor* activation, involves BDNF and adenosine signaling, preferentially affects pyramidal neurons , modulates astrocytes , microglia and cerebral blood flow* in animal studies [Islam et al., 1995; Radman et al., 2009; Fritsch et al., 2010; Wachter et al., 2011; Márquez-Ruiz et al., 2012; Rueger et al., 2012; Rohan et al., 2015; Monai et al., 2016; Pikhovych et al., 2016; Podda et al., 2016; Mishima et al., 2019; Gellner et al., 2021].	Modulates cortical connectivity* , oscillatory activity* , and interhemispheric* interactions in rodents [Reato et al., 2010; Sánchez-León et al., 2021a; Koo et al., 2016; Cambiaghi et al., 2020; Sun et al., 2020; Duan et al., 2022].
tACS	Induces synaptic plasticity through frequency-specific entrainment and STDP-like mechanisms* demonstrated in rodents and primates [Fujisawa et al., 2004; Ozen et al., 2010; Kar et al., 2017; Krause et al., 2019, 2022].	Engages neurotrophic factors (BDNF, GDNF), modulates glutamatergic and dopaminergic systems, involves AMPA receptors, NMDA receptors* , and acts in a frequency- and cell type-dependent manner, modulates microglia and enhances cerebral blood flow* in rodents [Fujisawa et al., 2004; Huang et al., 2021; Jeong et al., 2021; Turner et al., 2021; Lee et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2022; Lee et al., 2024].	Entrainment* of neuronal populations and modulation of network coherence demonstrated in rodents, influencing large-scale neural dynamics* [Ozen et al., 2010; Huang et al., 2021; Krause et al., 2022].
tRNS	Enhances plasticity via stochastic resonance* , reduces inhibitory neurotransmission, and promotes LTP-like effects* observed in rodents [Onorato et al., 2016; Remedios et al., 2019; Sánchez-León et al., 2021b].	Involves sodium channel activation* and GABAergic modulation independently of NMDA receptors*, as shown in <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> animal models [Remedios et al., 2019; Sánchez-León et al., 2021b].	Limited animal evidence suggests modulation of neuronal firing patterns and network-level activity* ; mechanistic insights are primarily derived from rodent studies [Remedios et al., 2019;

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165 Impact of tES on E/I Balance at the Synaptic Level

166 tES can modulate synaptic plasticity mechanisms essential for maintaining the E/I
167 balance. This balance is regulated by glutamate and GABA, acting through their
168 respective receptors (Isaacson & Scanziani, 2011), and is fine-tuned by neuromodulators
169 like acetylcholine, dopamine, and serotonin (Froemke, 2015). Disruptions in E/I balance
170 contribute to neurological and psychiatric disorders (Landau et al., 2016). By influencing
171 glutamatergic and GABAergic synapses, tES can enhance or suppress synaptic strength
172 depending on stimulation parameters and polarity (Nitsche et al., 2003; Fritsch et al.,
173 2010). These effects are mediated by long-term potentiation (LTP) and depression (LTD),
174 as conceptualized by Hebb (1949) and refined in models of spike-timing-dependent
175 plasticity (STDP) (Citri & Malenka, 2008; Dan & Poo, 2006). Through these mechanisms,
176 tES may help restore E/I balance in pathological conditions (Reato et al., 2013; Kronberg
177 et al., 2017).

178 tDCS induces polarity-dependent neuromodulatory effects, first demonstrated by
179 Bindman et al. (1964), who applied direct current to the cortex of anesthetized rats.
180 These effects were described in humans decades later by Nitsche & Paulus (2000) using
181 non-invasive stimulation. Their findings showed anodal tDCS enhances cortical
182 excitability, promoting LTP-like plasticity, while cathodal tDCS reduces excitability,
183 inducing LTD-like effects. Current evidence indicates tDCS effects depend not only on
184 polarity but also on neuronal orientation relative to the induced electric field. Maximal
185 effects occur when the somatodendritic axis aligns with the electric field (Bikson et al.,
186 2004; Kronberg et al., 2017; Sánchez-León et al., 2025). tACS modulates synaptic
187 plasticity by entraining neuronal activity at specific frequencies, reinforcing network
188 oscillations. This effect has been observed in rodent and primate models (Fujisawa et
189 al., 2004; Ozen et al., 2010; Krause et al., 2019, 2022). tACS-driven entrainment is
190 presumed to promote STDP-like plasticity, contributing to E/I balance regulation, as
191 suggested in both animal and human studies (Bland & Sale, 2019). tRNS applies

192 randomized high-frequency currents and has been proposed to enhance synaptic
193 plasticity via stochastic resonance, as demonstrated *in vitro* (Onorato et al., 2016). In
194 addition, tRNS has been shown to reduce inhibitory responses and promotes LTP-like
195 effects in humans (Van Der Groen & Wenderoth, 2016; Brancucci et al., 2023).
196 Furthermore, chronic tRNS decreases GABA levels in mice, suggesting plasticity-related
197 adaptations supporting long-term network reorganization (Sánchez-León et al., 2021b).
198 Factors influencing tRNS-induced plasticity remain incompletely characterized, but
199 human studies suggest intensity (Moliadze et al., 2012), frequency range (Fertonani et
200 al., 2011; Campana et al., 2016; Moret et al., 2019), and brain state during stimulation
201 (Jooß et al., 2016) significantly impact its effects.

202 By modulating synaptic plasticity, different tES protocols dynamically shift E/I balance,
203 promoting excitation or enhancing inhibition. Since synaptic plasticity is governed by
204 molecular and cellular events, we next explore how tES impacts these foundational
205 mechanisms.

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208 Molecular and Cellular Implications of tES on the E/I Balance

209 The effects of tES on the E/I balance extend beyond neuronal excitability, influencing
210 molecular pathways and cellular mechanisms that regulate synaptic plasticity. By
211 modulating ion channels, neurotransmitter systems, and neurotrophic factors, tES
212 induces adaptive molecular changes, which vary with stimulation modality and target
213 cell type. Figure 1 summarizes the immediate and long-term effects of each tES modality
214 on neuronal and glial components.

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217 **Figure 1. Physiological mechanisms underlying the immediate and long-term effects of tDCS,**
 218 **tACS, and tRNS. tDCS:** Immediate effects result from changes in membrane potential due to
 219 redistribution of intracellular charges by the applied current. Anodal stimulation depolarizes the
 220 somatic membrane near the axon initial segment, increasing excitability by making this region
 221 more positive. In contrast, cathodal stimulation hyperpolarizes the same region, decreasing
 222 excitability. Long-term effects depend on current polarity: anodal tDCS (red background)
 223 promotes LTP-like plasticity via NMDA receptors, BDNF, and adenosine. It also enhances
 224 cerebral blood flow and astrocytic calcium levels, facilitating synaptic plasticity and microglial
 225 motility. Cathodal tDCS (blue background) favors LTD-like plasticity through GABA and
 226 adenosine receptors, reduces blood flow, and promotes a more reactive microglial state. **tACS:**
 227 Immediate effects are characterized by neuronal entrainment to the applied oscillatory current,
 228 depending on frequency and phase. This is illustrated by synchronous neuronal firing (purple)
 229 and a non-entrained neuron (gray-purple). Long-term effects involve synaptic plasticity through
 230 spike-timing dependent plasticity (STDP), where the relative timing of pre- and post-synaptic
 231 spikes determines whether LTP- or LTD-like changes occur. tACS also increases cerebral blood

232 flow, potentially through activation of astrocytic, neuronal, or endothelial mechanisms, and
233 shifts microglial phenotype toward an anti-inflammatory profile. **tRNS:** Immediate effects arise
234 via stochastic resonance, whereby noise enhances the detection or transmission of weak signals.
235 In the subpanel, the top trace shows an oscillatory membrane potential (purple) remaining
236 below the threshold, with no action potentials generated. In contrast, the bottom trace
237 demonstrates how the addition of random noise (green) can cause the combined signal to
238 occasionally reach threshold, triggering action potentials. Long-term effects of tRNS may involve
239 repeated sodium channel activation, leading to sustained depolarization and LTP-like plasticity
240 at excitatory synapses. Additionally, LTD-like effects at inhibitory synapses may occur through
241 modulation of GABA_A receptors and decreased GABA release.

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243 The electrical current used in tES alters membrane polarization by redistributing
244 charges, which modulates ion channel activity and intracellular signaling (Ye & Steiger,
245 2015). In tDCS, anodal stimulation increases intracellular calcium—a key step in
246 plasticity—through calcium channels, while sodium channels mediate immediate effects
247 (Islam et al., 1995; Nitsche et al., 2003). NMDA receptor activation is also essential, as
248 shown *in vitro*, in animal models, and in humans (Islam et al., 1995; Liebetanz, 2002;
249 Nitsche et al., 2003; Rohan et al., 2015). Additionally, BDNF and adenosine contribute to
250 long-term synaptic changes in animal studies (Fritsch et al., 2010; Márquez-Ruiz et al.,
251 2012; Podda et al., 2016). Although the roles of BDNF and adenosine in tDCS have not
252 been directly demonstrated in humans, the Val66Met BDNF polymorphism—which
253 reduces BDNF release—has been associated with reduced plasticity after tDCS (Cheeran
254 et al., 2008). The molecular mechanisms of tACS remain less defined, but studies
255 indicate it modulates plasticity via neurotrophic and neurotransmitter systems. Beta-
256 tACS (20 Hz) improves motor deficits in Parkinson’s models by increasing GDNF and
257 activating neuroprotective pathways (Lee et al., 2022). Gamma-tACS (40 Hz) promotes
258 synaptic potentiation by engaging AMPA receptors, BDNF, and CREB (Jeong et al., 2021).
259 In humans, BDNF-dependent plasticity has been suggested to underlie some of the
260 effects of tACS, although further investigation is needed (Riddle et al., 2020). Given that
261 gamma oscillations rely on NMDA receptor activity, tACS may enhance synchronization
262 through glutamatergic signaling (Fujisawa et al., 2004). Supporting this, the involvement
263 of NMDA receptors in tACS-induced plasticity has also been demonstrated in humans

264 (Wischnewski et al., 2019). Although less understood, tRNS appears to involve repeated
265 sodium channel activation (Remedios et al., 2019) and reduced GABA release (Sánchez-
266 León, et al., 2021b). Unlike tDCS and tACS, it seems to act independently of NMDA
267 receptors, relying on sodium channels and GABAergic modulation, as seen in human
268 studies (Chaieb et al., 2015).

269 tES effects vary by neuronal cell type. tDCS primarily targets excitatory pyramidal
270 neurons, likely due to their elongated morphology, as shown *in vitro* (Radman et al.,
271 2009) and supported by computational models (Molaei-Ardekani et al., 2013). tACS
272 entrains pyramidal neurons at both low (8 Hz) and high (>100 Hz) frequencies, while
273 interneurons show subtype-specific frequency preferences: somatostatin-positive cells
274 respond to >30 Hz, and parvalbumin-positive cells to ~140 Hz, based on *in vivo* (Huang
275 et al., 2021) and *in vitro* (Lee et al., 2024) studies. For tRNS, *in vitro* data suggest effects
276 on pyramidal neurons (Remedios et al., 2019), while *in vivo* studies in awake animals
277 point to possible involvement of GABAergic interneurons (Sánchez-León et al., 2021).
278 Beyond neurons, tES also affects glial cells, crucial for synaptic homeostasis and
279 neuroinflammation. tDCS increases astrocytic calcium via adrenergic signaling and may
280 influence microglia through astrocyte–microglia interactions (Monai et al., 2016;
281 Mishima et al., 2019). It also modulates microglial activation and morphology, enhancing
282 motility and neuron–microglia signaling via the fractalkine pathway (Rueger et al., 2012;
283 Pikhovych et al., 2016; Gellner et al., 2021). tDCS alters cerebral blood flow, increasing
284 it after anodal and decreasing it after cathodal stimulation in animals (Wachter et al.,
285 2011) and in humans (Shinde et al., 2021). Similarly, tACS enhances cerebral perfusion
286 in a frequency- and dose-dependent manner through various mechanisms, including
287 neurovascular coupling, endothelial activation, astrocytic stimulation, and direct
288 neuronal effects (Turner et al., 2021). These effects have also been observed in humans
289 (Alekseichuk et al., 2016). Gamma-tACS reduces beta-amyloid plaques and promotes an
290 anti-inflammatory microglial phenotype, suggesting therapeutic potential in
291 neurodegeneration (Wu et al., 2022). While direct microglial changes have not been
292 confirmed in humans, a reduction of p-tau seen after 40 Hz tACS in Alzheimer’s patients
293 suggests microglial enhancement (Dhaynaut et al., 2022).

294 Modulation of the E/I balance by tES involves coordinated changes at the molecular and

295 cellular levels. The next section explores how these local effects extend to large-scale
296 network interactions that ultimately drive brain function.

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299 Modulation of the E/I Balance at the Neural Network Level

300 Beyond its local effects, tES influences large-scale network connectivity and oscillatory
301 activity, contributing to the modulation of the E/I balance at the neural network level.

302 These effects extend beyond the immediate stimulation site, altering both local and
303 distant brain regions and impacting functional and effective connectivity (Ozen et al.,
304 2010; Reato et al., 2010; Koo et al., 2016; Cambiaghi et al., 2020; Krause et al., 2022).

305 Among tES modalities, tDCS has been widely studied for its ability to modulate network
306 connectivity and oscillatory activity, thereby influencing global E/I balance. These effects
307 were first observed in humans (Antal et al., 2004) and later replicated in animals (Reato
308 et al., 2010). For instance, tDCS applied to the primary somatosensory cortex in mice
309 modulates gamma activity during and after stimulation, indicating plasticity changes
310 that could influence broader network dynamics (Sánchez-León et al., 2021a). Similarly,
311 in Alzheimer's disease models, prefrontal tDCS alters both alpha and gamma oscillations,
312 suggesting its potential to restore pathological E/I imbalances and impact
313 interconnected brain regions (Duan et al., 2022).

314 The network-wide effects of tDCS are linked to its layer-specific influence on cortical
315 circuits and its capacity to modulate interhemispheric and cortico-subcortical pathways.

316 tDCS effects are layer-dependent, with cathodal stimulation inducing LTD-like effects in
317 superficial layers and LTP-like effects in deeper ones, as shown in animal models (Sun et
318 al., 2020). Furthermore, tDCS influences distant regions through interhemispheric and
319 cortico-subcortical connectivity. For example, anodal tDCS applied to the left motor
320 cortex enhances contralateral excitability in rats, indicating plasticity-driven changes in
321 network interactions (Koo et al., 2016). Anodal prefrontal tDCS also modulates
322 serotonergic activity in the dorsal raphe nucleus, affecting neuromodulatory systems in
323 remote regions (Cambiaghi et al., 2020). This ability to influence distal regions has also
324 been confirmed in humans, where anodal prefrontal tDCS modulated activity in

325 subcortical and contralateral cortical areas (Weber et al., 2014). Like tDCS, tACS exerts
326 widespread effects beyond the stimulation site. In anesthetized rats, tACS entrains
327 neuronal firing across extensive cortical networks, demonstrating its capacity to
328 synchronize oscillatory activity at large scale (Ozen et al., 2010). Intrinsic network
329 dynamics can amplify tACS effects, enhancing its impact on E/I balance and long-range
330 connectivity, as supported by animal (Huang et al., 2021; Krause et al., 2022) and
331 humans studies (Chen et al., 2021; Diedrich et al., 2025). Although tRNS is relatively new,
332 human studies suggest it modulates neural oscillations. For example, tRNS over the
333 auditory cortex increased theta power in frontal and parietal regions, suggesting
334 potential network-wide modulation (Van Doren et al., 2014). However, the mechanisms
335 remain unclear, and further animal studies are needed to clarify its impact on network-
336 level E/I balance.

337 By modulating large-scale connectivity and oscillatory dynamics, tES reshapes the
338 brain's E/I balance, offering therapeutic potential for disorders characterized by E/I
339 dysregulation (Krause et al., 2013). Despite significant progress in understanding the
340 network-level effects of tES, important challenges remain that limit the extrapolation of
341 preclinical findings to human applications.

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344 Limitations and Future Perspectives

345 Studying the E/I balance using animal models presents inherent limitations due to
346 anatomical and physiological differences between animal and human brains. A major
347 challenge is the simpler geometry of animal cortices compared to the convoluted human
348 cortex, which affects both electrical field distribution and large-scale network dynamics.
349 For example, rodents' smaller brains and lack of cortical gyri limit direct extrapolation
350 to humans. Moreover, scaling issues in tES protocols often require higher current
351 densities in animals, influenced by differences in neuronal density, axonal architecture,
352 and cortical organization (Ozen et al., 2010; Vöröslakos et al., 2018; Asan et al., 2020).
353 Stimulation durations also vary substantially, as preclinical studies typically employ
354 shorter sessions than clinical protocols, complicating the assessment of long-term

355 effects (Johnson et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2021).

356 Efforts are underway to bridge these gaps. Studies in non-human primates provide more
357 translatable data on behavior, electric field distribution, and neural dynamics (Opitz et
358 al., 2016; Krause et al., 2017). In rodents, lowering current densities (Bolzoni et al., 2013;
359 Farahani et al., 2024) and incorporating human-relevant behavioral tasks (Márquez-Ruiz
360 et al., 2012, 2016; Kar et al., 2017) have improved translational validity. Furthermore,
361 animal models remain indispensable for mechanistic research at the synaptic and
362 network levels—insights not easily attainable in humans (Jackson et al., 2016; Sánchez-
363 León et al., 2018). Importantly, these experimental findings provide the biological
364 foundation for developing computational models that simulate how tES modulates
365 neuronal activity. By incorporating data on cellular and network-level mechanisms from
366 animal studies, such models can help extrapolate stimulation effects to the human brain
367 and guide protocol optimization with improved anatomical and physiological accuracy.

368 Future research should prioritize methodological refinement. Using computational
369 modeling to estimate electric fields more accurately, adjusting stimulation parameters
370 accordingly, and aligning experimental designs with disease-specific biomarkers will be
371 key to increasing the translational value of animal studies. Integrating advanced
372 neurotechnologies into these models can further accelerate progress toward clinically
373 meaningful applications of tES.

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376 Conclusions

377 In summary, tES is a promising neuromodulatory approach with significant potential for
378 both basic neuroscience and clinical translation. By modulating the E/I balance, it
379 influences synaptic plasticity, circuit function, and network synchronization, offering a
380 powerful tool to probe and treat neurological and psychiatric conditions. Insights from
381 animal models have elucidated key mechanisms underlying tES effects, including
382 polarity-dependent modulation by tDCS, frequency-specific entrainment by tACS, and
383 the emerging utility of tRNS.

384 These findings underscore the value of preclinical research for identifying how tES
385 interacts with glutamatergic and GABAergic systems, supports oscillatory coherence,
386 and shapes brain dynamics. Moving forward, combining tES with complementary
387 approaches—such as pharmacological, genetic, or behavioral interventions—may
388 enhance specificity and therapeutic efficacy. Continued integration of mechanistic
389 insights will be essential to realize personalized neuromodulation strategies and
390 improve clinical outcomes in disorders characterized by disrupted E/I balance.

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